

Figure 1: Image of Luminous Fast Blue Optical Transient (LFBOT) from Gemini/NASA/ESA press release. Credit: NASA/ESA/NSF's NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/ M. Garlick /M. Zamani

Luminous Fast Blue Optical Transients: The Finch and Other Animals

Ashley Chrimes (ESA/ESTEC), Peter Jonker (Radboud University),
and Andrew Levan (Radboud University)

This year we defined a multi-facility joint observing program to characterize a new Luminous Fast Blue Optical Transient (LFBOT) in detail. The program included time on the International Gemini Observatory, the *Hubble Space Telescope*, the Very Large Array, and the Chandra X-ray Observatory. On April 10, a new LFBOT candidate was discovered by ZTF (the Zwicky Transient Facility) — AT2023fhn (“the Finch”). Following reports that it had a featureless spectrum, we triggered our program, obtaining Gemini, *Hubble*, and Chandra data shortly after. A Chandra X-ray detection confirmed the LFBOT nature of the event. From ground-based observations, the location of the transient appeared to be consistent with a galaxy at $z = 0.24$. The high angular resolution of *Hubble*, however, revealed the object to have a large angular offset from two nearby galaxies — an unusual place to find a core-collapse event, which was a favored explanation for LFBOTs. Gemini

spectroscopy was crucial in demonstrating that the fainter, presumed satellite galaxy was at the same redshift as the brighter galaxy, a barred spiral.

With the advent of wide-field, high-cadence, and deep-sky surveyors (e.g., ZTF, ATLAS, GOTO, BlackGEM), the discovery of rapidly evolving transients has become possible. Fast evolving (>0.3 magnitudes per day) and blue ($g-r < -0.3$) transients with follow-up spectroscopy are typically found to be infant supernovae. But in 2018, a new class of transient with these features was discovered. AT2018cow — colloquially known as the “the Cow” — was fast and blue and had a featureless, hot spectrum at early times. The host galaxy yielded a redshift, giving an absolute magnitude of ~ -21 — much brighter than regular supernovae. The event also produced bright X-ray and radio emission. This combination of properties was unlike

Figure 2: Gemini spectra of AT2023fhn and the satellite galaxy. Credit: Chrimes et al. 2023

any transient seen before. Such transients are now discovered at a rate of 1–2 per year and are known as Cow-like, or luminous fast blue optical transients (Ho et al. 2023). Their key feature is the inability for ^{56}Ni decay models to explain both the rapid lightcurve decay and the peak absolute magnitude, in addition to the X-rays (implying the presence of a central engine) and long-lasting radio emission (pointing towards a dense, extended circumstellar medium). Models invoked to explain LFBOTs include ultra-stripped supernovae with a central engine, the tidal disruption of a white dwarf around an intermediate mass black hole (IMBH), or the merger of a black hole and Wolf-Rayet star. Despite growing interest, none of the events following AT2018cow (e.g., the Koala, Camel, or Tasmanian Devil) were observed in as much detail (but neither were any as nearby).

The location of the Finch is atypical for any of the leading LFBOT theories. Neither massive stars nor IMBHs are expected at such large spatial offsets from their host galaxies, but neither is the offset so large as to completely rule out either scenario. Furthermore, the presence of an underlying stellar cluster, hosting the transient but presently outshined by it, cannot be ruled out.

The origin of the Finch — and the other LFBOTs so far — therefore remains uncertain. The discovery of UV and X-ray emission from AT2018cow several years afterwards points towards an accreting black hole as the central engine, but the origin of the black hole (formed in the event or pre-existing?), the material being accreted (white dwarf, stellar envelope?), and its mass (stellar or intermediate?) remain unknown. Detailed observations of future LFBOTs, ideally those nearby, like AT2018cow, are crucial to narrow down their environments, emission processes, and, ultimately, progenitors.

This article describes the observing program presented in Chrimes et al. (2023), which includes the following co-authors: Deanne Coppejans (University of Warwick), Nicola Gaspari (Radboud University), Ben Gompertz (University of Birmingham), Paul Groot (Radboud University), Daniele Malesani (University of Copenhagen), Andrew Mummery (University of Oxford), Elizabeth Stanway (University of Warwick), and Klaas Wiersema (University of Hertfordshire).

References

- Chrimes, A. A. et al. 2023, *MNRAS*, 527, L47
 Ho et al. 2023, *ApJ*, 949, 120

Figure 3: Hubble images (~g and ~r band) of the transient location. Credit: Chrimes et al. 2023